

Tabla. Compendio de estudios primarios resultado de la revisión bola de nieve hacia atrás.

Id	Artículo	N.C	Año	Ref.
E16	ChatGPT Prompt Patterns for Improving Code Quality, Refactoring, Requirements Elicitation, and Software Design	409	2024	[29]
E17	Conversing with Copilot: Exploring Prompt engineering for Solving CS1 Problems Using Natural Language	341	2023	[4]
E18	Training language models to follow instructions with human feedback	13	2022	[30]
E19	Prompt-Enhanced Software Vulnerability Detection Using ChatGPT	80	2024	[31]
E20	Self-Planning Code Generation with Large Language Models	192	2024	[32]
E21	On the Robustness of Code Generation Techniques: An Empirical Study on GitHub Copilot	156	2023	[33]
E22	Grounded Copilot: How Programmers Interact with Code-Generating Models	445	2023	[34]
E23	AI Chains: Transparent and Controllable Human-AI Interaction by Chaining Large Language Model Prompts	606	2022	[5]
E24	My AI Wants to Know if This Will Be on the Exam: Testing OpenAI's Codex on CS2 Programming Exercises	181	2023	[9]
E25	Evaluating LLM-generated Worked Examples in an Introductory Programming Course	71	2024	[35]
E26	Studying the effect of AI Code Generators on Supporting Novice Learners in Introductory Programming	303	2023	[36]
E27	Automatic Generation of Programming Exercises and Code Explanations Using Large Language Models	537	2022	[37]
E28	Prompt Programming for Large Language Models: Beyond the Few-Shot Paradigm	1159	2021	[11]

Acronimos usados: Id = Identificador del Estudio, NC = Número de Citaciones, Ref. = Referencias.